

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

**Do pandemics have a benefit on
the environment? Analyzing the
Relation between Covid-19
mobility Restrictions and CO2
emissions**

COV_MOB

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		<p>This DMP is licensed under a <u>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License</u> (CC BY 4.0).</p> <p>It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.17672942</p>
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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1.Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Joined Air Quality and Movement Dataset	Other	NetCDF	5 - 10 GB	no
P2	Regression Analysis Results	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	Source Code	Source code	.py	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Joined Air Quality and Movement Dataset":

Final analytical dataset generated from the original movement dataset provided by google and The environmental data provided by the EU. Contains multidimensional scientific data such as temperature, CO2 emission levels, movement index and links them to european countries at a certain time between 1. 1. 2020 and 15. 10. 2022.

Description for "Regression Analysis Results":

Results of Multivariate Regression Models for each European country. The file contains information about the package/model used, the predictor, coefficients, standard errors, p values and sample size. There will be one csv file generated for each country and all of them will be stored in the same directory. In the same directory there will also be a readme.md file containing metadata describing the structure and naming of the files.

All of the files will follow a consistent naming convention which is to be defined. The readmes will follow googles readme style guides.

Description for "Source Code":

Source code containing all of the data processing steps and the code for the Plotly Visualizations. Documentation is available in the form of a project Level ReadMe.md file. The repository structure will follow the Cookie cutter data science convention. The repository will contain python 3.12 code, Readme.md files and package management metadata files produced by UV. All of the files will follow a consistent naming convention which is to be defined. The readme will follow googles style guide

Technical resources for "Source Code":

Cookie Cutter Data Science: <https://github.com/drivendataorg/cookiecutter-data-science>

Googles Style guide: <https://google.github.io/styleguide/docguide/READMEs.html>

Technical resources for "Joined Air Quality and Movement Dataset":

NetCDF documentation: <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf>

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	COVID-19 Mobility Community Reports	https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/		no
R2	European Environment Agency Air Quality Dataset	https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/		no

Description for "COVID-19 Mobility Community Reports":

These Community Mobility Reports aimed to provide insights into what changed in response to policies aimed at combating COVID-19. The reports charted movement trends over time by geography, across different categories of places such as retail and recreation, groceries and pharmacies, parks, transit stations, workplaces, and residential. Provided by Google LLC under the CC-BY 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) license

Description for "European Environment Agency Air Quality Dataset":

Air quality measurements time series reported by European member countries. Limited to dates between 1. 1. 2020 and 15. 10. 2022 Provided by Pan European (EEA) License CC-BY 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright holder: European Environment Agency (EEA).

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Research data will be generated by downloading two existing external datasets, which will be reused in accordance with their licence terms. Based on the Original dataset sources, both of the datasets should be available indefinitely. The data will be filtered, cleaned, transformed and then aggregated and joined to produce the final analytical datasets. The project will follow a directory hierarchy separating raw, processed, and final datasets to ensure traceability and data provenance. All processing and analysis will be carried out using Python 3.12 with standard and freely available scientific libraries, including Pandas and NumPy. Full source code and the documentation detailing the steps to run it will be made available on Gitlab to ensure reproducibility.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

Data versioning will be managed using DVC (Data Version Control), which will track all dataset states. The original (raw) data will always be stored unchanged. The project will follow a directory hierarchy separating raw, processed, and final datasets to ensure a clear workflow and traceability. Filenames will follow a structured and consistently applied naming convention, which will be fully defined during the project setup. This approach ensures that every transformation step, from initial downloads through filtering and aggregation to the final datasets used for analysis and visualisation, can be reproduced and verified.

The final analytics dataset is provided in the NetCDF format, which is self describing meaning that it already contains the metadata needed for understanding the data. For the statistical analysis csv files there will be a ReadMe.md file provided with detailed descriptions located in same directory as the csv files. It will contain information of the column names, data types and the overall structure of the file. The decision to use the readme.md file was made because there don't seem to be any appropriate metadata standards for this field. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The source code will be made available using a public gitlab repository hosted at TU Wien. There will be a project level pyproject.toml file containing all of the used package versions as well as a .python-version file containing the used python version. There will also be included a project level readme file containing the steps needed to run the code and reproduce the results, the authors of the repository, the relevant license and also other important contextual assumptions made during implementation. All of the readme files will follow googles readme style guide (<https://google.github.io/styleguide/docguide/READMEs.html>).

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Tibor Cus (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P3 (Source Code) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

R1 (COVID-19 Mobility Community Reports), R2 (European Environment Agency Air

Quality Dataset), P1 (Joined Air Quality and Movement Dataset), P2 (Regression Analysis Results) will be stored on TUcloud-Spaces: TUcloud-Spaces is a sync&share service for projects provided by Campus IT. Only authorised staff members and project partners will have access to the TUcloud-Spaces folders. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days by using the bin function.

R1 (COVID-19 Mobility Community Reports), R2 (European Environment Agency Air Quality Dataset), P1 (Joined Air Quality and Movement Dataset), P2 (Regression Analysis Results) will be backed up on TuFiles daily. Tufiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by Campus IT

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	writing	reading only	reading only
R2	writing	reading only	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The person with the right to control access to data will be Tibor Cus, the Only Member of the Project, who is also the Project Lead

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open, embargo until 2026-01-31	2025-12-30	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/d7sy1-kdr47	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open, embargo until 2026-01-31	2025-12-30	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/g1fc4-fm535	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open, private until 2026-01-31	2025-12-30	TU Wien GitLab	https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at/e12325298/cov_mob	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: All of the re-used dataset are freely available only as is the code for reproducing the analysis. The project requires only free open source software, so anyone should be able to reproduce it on the condition that they are able to install and use python. The data will be published under the CC BY (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) license, so there are no restrictions for reuse as long as the original author is cited.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The target audience can range from

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
			governments, health officials, students as well as the general public. Mostly we aim to provide analytical results helping governments to design better policies in reaction to pandemics. The data could also be potentially reused for other goals such as logistics or social sciences.
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The target audience can range from governments, health officials, students as well as the general public. Mostly we aim to provide analytical results helping governments to design better policies in reaction to pandemics. The data could also be potentially reused for other goals such as logistics or social sciences.
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The target audience can range from governments, health officials, students as well as the general public. Mostly we aim to provide analytical results helping governments to design better policies in reaction to pandemics. The data could also be potentially reused for other goals such as logistics or social sciences.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Project Lead will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.